

Buckling and Postbuckling Behavior of Composite Laminates with an Embedded Delamination

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ABSTRACT

A finite element modeling is presented to study the buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates with an embedded delamination. The buckling and postbuckling behavior of graphite/epoxy composite laminates with an embedded delamination are investigated for various delamination sizes, stacking sequence and boundary conditions. Three different possible modes of instability are identified at the critical load, which is global, mixed, and local buckling mode. The buckling load and postbuckling behavior depend on the buckling mode that is determined by the delamination size, stacking sequence and boundary conditions. It is found that the presence of a delamination in composite laminates may induce couplings, which have significant effects on the buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing use of composite laminates, compression behavior of delaminated structures has received considerable attention in recent years. Several authors have investigated various aspects of the buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates with a delamination. Most of the papers on the delamination buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates are limited to a through-the-width or a near-surface delamination, which are employed by one-dimensional model[1-5] or thin-film approximation[6-8]. In actual situations, however, impact causes embedded delaminations that can not be employed by one-dimensional model or thin-film approximation. Therefore, there is need for a capability that can be applied to general delamination with complex geometry. In present paper, a finite element modeling is presented to study the buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates with an embedded delamination by a two-dimensional theory. Because of geometric complexity and large deformation in the postbuckling state of the laminate, a geometrically nonlinear finite element analysis is performed. It is assumed that delamination exists before loading and that delamination growth is ignored. Such an assumption is valid for overall compression behavior of composite laminates. The buckling and postbuckling behavior of graphite/epoxy composite laminates with an embedded delamination are investigated for various delamination sizes, stacking sequence and boundary conditions.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The configuration of the laminate is shown in Figure 1. Because of the presence of an embedded delamination, the laminate is divided into three regions referred separately as base laminate, lower and upper sublaminates. Therefore, three-dimensional finite element analysis is required. A finite element modeling, presented in this paper, is that the three separate regions are modeled by degenerated shell elements located along the mid-planes of each of these regions. The degenerated shell element is obtained from the three-dimensional solid element by imposing two constraints: 1) straight lines normal to the mid-plane before deformation remain straight but not normal after deformation; and 2) the transverse normal components of stress are ignored. These assumptions degenerate a three-dimensional theory to a two-dimensional theory, and the degenerated shell element is called three-dimensional degenerated shell element.

Two basic assumptions should be satisfied in the thickness direction along the delamination front during deformation. Therefore, all vertical displacements and all rotations are equal in the thickness direction along the delamination front. Also, the displacements u and v can be related to each other by the rotation angle and the vertical distance between the respective mid-planes. The following compatibility relations are obtained at nodes in the thickness direction along the delamination front:

$$w = w_1 = w_2 = w_3 \tag{1}$$

$$\theta_x = \theta_{x1} = \theta_{x2} = \theta_{x3} \tag{2}$$

$$\theta_y = \theta_{y1} = \theta_{y2} = \theta_{y3} \tag{3}$$

$$u_2 = u_1 - h_l \theta_x, \quad u_3 = u_1 + h_u \theta_y \tag{4}$$

$$v_2 = v_1 + h_l \theta_y, \quad v_3 = v_1 - h_u \theta_x \tag{5}$$

where u , v and w are the displacements of x -, y - and z - directions, respectively, as shown in Figure 1. θ_x and θ_y are the rotations about x - and y -axes, respectively. The subscripts, 1, 2 and 3 denote base laminate, lower and upper sublaminates, respectively. h_l and h_u are the distances of the lower and upper mid-planes of sublaminates, respectively, from the mid-plane of base laminate. These constraints in the thickness direction along the delamination front are satisfied by implementation of rigid beam element. A typical finite element modeling is shown in Figure 2.

FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

At an arbitrary $(n + 1)$ th equilibrium state, the principle of virtual work is expressed as

$$\iiint_{V^{n+1}} \sigma_{ij}^{n+1} \delta e_{ij}^{n+1} dV = \iiint_{V^{n+1}} f_i^{n+1} \delta u_i^{n+1} dV + \iint_{S_T^{n+1}} T_i^{n+1} \delta u_i^{n+1} dS \tag{6}$$

where σ_{ij} , e_{ij} , f_i , T_i , u_i and δ are the Cauchy stress, infinitesimal strain, body force, surface traction, displacement and variation operator, respectively. In the case of no body force, equation (6) can be rewritten in terms of increments of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress, S_{ij} and the Green strain, ϵ_{ij} . Using the updated Lagrangian description taking the configuration at n th equilibrium state as the reference one, equation (6) is expressed as

$$\iiint_{V_n} (\sigma_{ij}^n + \Delta S_{ij}) \delta(\Delta \epsilon_{ij}) dV - \iint_{S_n^*} (T_i^n + \Delta T_i) \delta(\Delta u_i) dS = 0 \quad (7)$$

The eight-node degenerated shell element is utilized for the finite element modeling. Nodal degrees of freedom are three translational displacements (u, v, w) in the global x, y - and z -directions and two rotations (β_1, β_2) about the local unit vectors. In using this element for the finite element formulation, no specific shell theory is employed except for two basic assumptions that the lines originally normal to the mid-plane remain straight and that the transverse normal stress remains zero. Incremental displacement fields in an element are expressed as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta u \\ \Delta v \\ \Delta w \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{n=1}^8 H_n(\xi, \eta) \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta u_n \\ \Delta v_n \\ \Delta w_n \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^8 H_n(\xi, \eta) t_n \zeta \{ \Delta V_{3n} \} \quad (8)$$

where ξ, η, ζ are local coordinates in the element. $H_n(\xi, \eta), t_n$ and $\{ \Delta V_{3n} \}$ are shape function, thickness and increment of the vector in 3-direction at n th node, respectively.

From equation (7), the incremental finite element equation[9] is derived as

$$([K_L] + [K_{NL}]) \{ \Delta U_n \} = - \{ \Delta P \} \quad (9)$$

where $[K_L], [K_{NL}], \{ \Delta U_n \}$, and $\{ \Delta P \}$ are the linear element stiffness matrix, nonlinear element stiffness matrix, vector of nodal incremental displacements, and incremental load, respectively. After assembling element stiffness matrices, and load vectors, a combined method of Newton-Raphson and modified Newton-Raphson method is employed to solve the equations iteratively until the actual equations of equilibrium are satisfied to a required tolerance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

$[0//0/0/0]_T$ laminate with a through-the-width delamination between two clamped edges is considered to compare the finite element modeling with an analytic solution, and to describe mechanics of the buckling and postbuckling behavior. Double slash "/" represents the position of a delamination within the laminate. The laminate has the length of $L = 150$ mm, the width of $W = 10$ mm, and the thickness of one ply of $t_p = 0.125$ mm.

In the following, the circular delamination is assumed to simplify an embedded delamination. $[0//0/0/0]_T, [0//90/90/0]_T, [0//90_s/0]_T$, and $[0//90/(\pm 45)_s/90/0]_T$ laminates are considered to characterize the effects of delamination size, stacking sequence and boundary conditions on the buckling and postbuckling behavior of the laminate. Boundary conditions at four edges are considered as both all clamped and all simply supported. The laminate has the length of $L = 150$ mm, the width of $W = 150$ mm, and the thickness of one ply of $t_p = 0.125$ mm. Engineering constants of graphite/epoxy for the present analysis are as follows:

$$E_1 = 135.4 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_2 = E_3 = 9.6 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.8 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{23} = 3.2 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.31, \quad \nu_{23} = 0.52.$$

Extremely small transverse load in center of the upper sublaminar is applied to make initial imperfection, which induces buckling upwardly to prevent overlapping of the upper and lower sublaminar. The axial compressive load is applied in the form of a uniform displacement-increase in end displacement.

THROUGH-THE -WIDTH DELAMINATION

For validation of the finite element modeling, the present finite element analysis is compared with an analytic solution [4]. The analytic solution is employed based on the one-dimensional beam theory and formulated by a variational energy principle. The results of the present analysis and analytic solution for the buckling load and postbuckling behavior are given in Figures 3-4. The buckling load is normalized with respect to Euler buckling load P_0 for perfect plate. It can be seen that the finite element modeling predicts well the buckling load and equilibrium path in the postbuckling state. In Figure 4, it is observed that the difference between the present nonlinear finite element analysis and linear analytic solution is shown in the range of large deflection.

The buckling and postbuckling behavior of the laminate with a through-the-width delamination are described in terms of a delamination length and reaction moment, i.e., bending moment at $x=0$. The laminate is loaded, and three different possible modes of instability can be readily identified at the critical load, which are global, mixed, and local buckling mode. It depends on delamination length. Global buckling preceding any other instability mode occurs for a relatively small delamination length [5]. On the other hand, if the length of the delamination is relatively large, then local buckling of the upper sublaminar precedes any other mode of instability because the delamination is sufficiently slender in comparison with the whole laminate. In this case, significant out-of-plane deflection occurs mainly in the upper sublaminar. This mode has been referred to as thin film delamination. Mixed buckling involving out-of-plane deflections for both the sublaminars and the base laminate, a combination of the two modes, takes place in the intermediate delamination length between global buckling and local buckling. It is an interesting phenomenon that the reaction moment increases drastically at buckling point. When global or mixed buckling mode governs buckling, both the upper and lower sublaminars deflect upward in the postbuckling state because the reaction moment is on the increase upwardly. When local buckling mode governs buckling, both the upper and lower sublaminars deflect upward in initial postbuckling state. However, a transition point exists in the postbuckling state, as discussed by Yin et al.[2] for long and thin delaminations. Beyond the transition point, the upper and lower sublaminars begin to deflect in opposite direction, i.e., the lower sublaminar and base laminate turn to deflect downward when the value of reaction moment is negative. When local buckling mode governs buckling, it is seen that as the delamination length increases, the maximum upward deflection of lower sublaminar decreases in the initial postbuckling state because the positive maximum reaction moment decreases.

EMBEDDED DELAMINATION

Figure 5 shows the effects of delamination size and boundary conditions on the buckling load and buckling mode for composite laminars. Clamped and simply supported boundary conditions are considered for the present analysis. Thin film approximation[6-8] is results of ANSYS(a commercial finite element code). From these results, it is seen that the buckling load decreases as the delamination size increases, and that there exists a delamination size by which the

buckling load is not affected, i.e., critical delamination size. In $[0//90/90/0]_T$ laminate, the buckling load is considerably smaller than that of $[0//0/0/0]_T$ laminate, since the presence of a delamination in $[0//90/90/0]_T$ laminate induces extension-bending couplings. In the simply supported boundary condition, the presence of a delamination has less influence on the buckling load than that of the clamped one. Both the critical delamination size and the delamination size for which local buckling occurs are very larger than those of the clamped one, since the simply supported one is boundary condition that induces easily global buckling. The buckling mode that depends on the delamination size and boundary condition is related to the buckling load. Namely, the buckling load does not decrease appreciably at the delamination size for which global buckling mode occurs. If the delamination size is larger than the critical delamination size, the buckling load begins to decrease and mixed buckling mode occurs instead of global buckling mode. At the delamination size for which local buckling mode occurs, the buckling load is greatly affected and it drops drastically. As shown in Figure 5, it is seen that thin film approximation can predict the buckling load for the local buckling mode, which cannot be employed in predicting the buckling load if local buckling mode does not govern buckling.

Figure 6 shows the effects of delamination on the postbuckling behavior. Bifurcation buckling occurs for $[0//90/90/0]_T$ laminate which is unsymmetric, like $[0//0/0/0]_T$ symmetric laminate. This is because the upper and lower sublaminates have elastically supported boundary to base laminate. It is confirmed [10] that unsymmetric laminate under axial loading is to remain flat when edge constraints are capable of supplying the necessary bending moments and twisting moments. From the results presented, there exists three types of the postbuckling behavior, which depend on the buckling mode. When global buckling mode governs buckling, the postbuckling behavior is not affected by the presence of a delamination. When mixed buckling mode governs buckling, both the upper and lower sublaminates deflect upward in the postbuckling state. As compressive load is increased, the buckling deformation relieves the load in the upper sublaminate and aggravates the load in the lower sublaminate. Eventually, these two sublaminates come into contact. The state of contact appears when increasing reaction moment is equal to that of global buckling mode as shown in Figure 7. After contact state, the postbuckling behavior is identical to that of global buckling mode. This means that delamination growth, unless it occurs before contact state, is not expected to occur with continuing deformation. When local buckling mode governs buckling, both the upper and lower sublaminates deflect upward in initial postbuckling state. However, beyond the transition point, the upper and lower sublaminates begin to deflect in opposite direction due to the reaction moment, i.e., the lower sublaminate and base laminate turn to deflect downward, when the value of reaction moment is negative. As the difference between the deflections of the upper and lower sublaminates is larger in the postbuckling state when local buckling mode governs buckling, it may lead to delamination growth. It is can be seen that even though the upper sublaminate is buckled, the laminate is still capable of supporting a higher load if delamination growth depending on the buckling mode and material toughness is not likely to occur.

The effects of extension-bending couplings induced by a delamination are also illustrated in Figure 8. The buckling load in $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate is smaller than that of $[0/90]_S$ because bending-twisting couplings exist in $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate. It is well known that bending-twisting couplings reduce the buckling loads of composite laminates. However, the buckling load in $[0//90/0/0]_T$ laminate is considerably smaller than that of $[0//90/(\pm 45)_S/90/0]_T$ laminates, since extension-bending couplings in $[0//90/0/0]_T$ laminate is larger than that of $[0//90/(\pm 45)_S/90/0]_T$ laminates. Extension-bending couplings induced by a delamination have significant effects on the buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an efficient finite element modeling is presented to study the buckling and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates with an embedded delamination. The modeling is capable of predicting accurate buckling load and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates with an embedded delamination. The effects of delamination on the buckling load and postbuckling behavior of composite laminates are studied.

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Fig. 1 Configuration of composite laminates with a delamination.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of the finite element modeling of composite laminates with a delamination.

Fig. 3 Buckling loads of $[0//0/0/0]_T$ laminates with a through-the-width delamination.

Fig. 4 Midpoint deflections of upper and lower sublaminates of $[0//0/0/0]_T$ laminate with a through-the-width delamination.

Fig. 5 Buckling loads and modes for various delamination sizes in composite laminates.

Fig. 6 Midpoint deflections of upper and lower sublaminates for various delamination sizes in $[0//90/90/0]_T$ laminate with all clamped boundary edges.

Fig. 7 Reaction moments for various delamination sizes in $[0//0/0/0]_T$ laminates with all clamped boundary edges.

Fig. 8 Buckling loads and modes for various delamination sizes in composite laminates with all clamped boundary edges.